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Materials (list titles) (additional materials/titles may be listed on the appendix which must be attached or printed on reverse side of this form.)

Robert E. Gibboney: A Life Etched in Stone and Storm

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Permission to Duplicate Form --- Appendix

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	Titles	TN (FamilySearch use only)
1	Robert E. Gibboney: A Life Etched in Stone and Storm	
2	Dorothea "Doris" Dorschke: A Life Etched in Time	
3	Joseph Godfrey Swartz (1847-1887): Scholar of the Valley, Son of a Vanished Cause	
4	"God's Will": My Family Connection to Confederate General Robert E. Lee	
5	Norman Allen Langley Biography	
6	Wings of Valor: The Life and Legacy of Major Francis Aubrey Swartz	
7	Wanda Lou Dawson: A Life Between Shadows and Light	
8	Marie Ellen Dawson Biography	
9	Gerd Edwin Paul Kaess Biography	
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